

Relevance of resources' access in gender enterprises' operational management: The Namibian case.¹

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Abstract

This article investigates the role of gender in the operational management of enterprises in Namibia by analysing access to key managerial resources—finance, land, and information and communication technologies (ICT)—using data from the 2014/2015 Namibia Enterprise Survey. The study applies a test of independence to assess whether gender differences significantly affect enterprise access to these resources. In addition, it examines perceptions of corruption as a potential barrier to resource access. The results reveal no statistically significant gender differences in several aspects of resource access. However, significant disparities are observed in land ownership, land access, and the perceived challenges related to telecommunications, with male-managed enterprises reporting higher rates of land ownership and greater obstacles in land and ICT accessibility. These findings are situated within Namibia's historical context of gendered inequalities and its contemporary policy frameworks promoting gender equity. The study further draws on Equity Theory from Human Resource Management, highlighting how perceptions of fairness—or unfairness—in resource distribution influence enterprise behaviour and managerial motivation. The analysis suggests that while formal equality has advanced, substantive barriers remain. Nonetheless, shifting patterns in gendered experiences of obstacles, especially among male entrepreneurs, may indicate evolving masculinities and the emergence of a new, more egalitarian normal. The article concludes that gender equity in enterprise development does not emerge spontaneously but must be intentionally constructed and continuously assessed to ensure transformative outcomes.

Keywords: Gender; enterprise; resource access; equity theory; Namibia; operational management; human resources management.

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1.0 Introductory background

This study investigates how gender facilitates or hinders access to critical resources and, in turn, impacts the operational management of enterprises in Namibia. Operations management—defined as the planning, organising, coordinating, and controlling of resources to produce goods and services—is central to enterprise success (Reid & Sanders, 2012). However, as Blaikie et al. (1994:48) emphasise, resource presence alone is insufficient; what matters is the capacity to access and effectively use those resources.

Gender inequality remains deeply embedded in global social, political, and economic structures (UN Women, 2020). Across many societies, historical constructions of gender roles have privileged male dominance, limiting women’s access to decision-making, ownership, and productive assets (Connell, 2005). In Africa, these gender asymmetries were reinforced by colonial institutions, customary laws, and patriarchal norms that collectively marginalised women from full participation in economic life (Mama, 2001; Tamale, 2020). The intersectionality of gender with race, class, and ethnicity has further intensified these disadvantages, especially in rural and marginalised contexts (Crenshaw, 1991; Tsikata, 2009). Consequently, gender disparities continue to shape access to education, employment, and entrepreneurial opportunities, locking many women into cycles of disempowerment (Bhana et al., 2021).

Despite these structural legacies, post-independence African states, including Namibia, have introduced constitutional and policy reforms aimed at redressing gender imbalances. Article 10 of the Namibian Constitution guarantees equality before the law and prohibits discrimination on the basis of sex, race, and other social attributes. Institutional mechanisms such as the Employment Equity Commission have been established to monitor compliance and promote gender parity in the workplace. Namibia’s performance on the Global Gender Gap Index reflects notable progress: in 2022, the country ranked 8th globally with a score of 0.807. However, this marked a decline from previous years, particularly due to persistent gaps in women’s labour force participation, wage equality, and income levels (World Economic Forum, 2022).

While formal legal equality has advanced, substantive inequalities persist. For instance, female participation in enterprise ownership stood at 41% in 2015, yet actual female ownership was only 26% (Venditto et al., 2020). This discrepancy suggests that despite policy efforts and statistical gains in representation, deeper structural and cultural barriers continue to hinder women’s full economic agency. As such, the question remains: do gendered structures still disadvantage women in accessing the resources necessary for effective enterprise management?

This article examines access to three pivotal resources: finance, land, and ICT. These are essential components of enterprise operations, yet often distributed unevenly across gender lines. Furthermore, because corruption influences how resources are allocated and accessed in many business environments, it is also included in the analysis. By drawing on the Namibia Enterprise Survey data collected by the World Bank (2014–2015), this study investigates whether gender continues to influence operational management outcomes, and how these patterns might reflect ongoing or shifting gender dynamics in Namibia’s enterprise landscape. From a human resource management perspective, understanding how individuals perceive fairness in resource access can also help explain differences in enterprise motivation, performance, and leadership efficacy—areas which Equity Theory helps illuminate.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature on gendered access to finance, land, ICT, and

the influence of corruption on enterprise management. Section 3 situates the Namibian enterprise context. Section 4 outlines the methodological framework and data sources. Section 5 presents the empirical findings, followed by Section 6 which discusses the implications and offers concluding reflections and recommendations.

2 Gendered resource access and human resource management perspectives

Access to productive resources plays a critical role in determining the success or failure of entrepreneurial ventures. Once a business opportunity has been identified, entrepreneurs must mobilise both financial (e.g., capital and land) and non-financial (e.g., human and social capital) resources. The ability to access and control these resources is crucial for business start-up, growth, and sustainability (Kedmenec et al., 2014; Paul & Meena, 2016). However, such access is frequently mediated by gendered structures that determine who is included or excluded from resource ownership and utilisation. This section focuses on four dimensions—financial inclusion, land accessibility, ICT use, and corruption—each of which significantly affects enterprise operations and may exhibit gendered patterns of disparity.

The analysis of gendered access to enterprise resources can also benefit from insights drawn from Human Resource Management (HRM), particularly Equity Theory (Adams, 1963). This theory posits that individuals evaluate fairness in resource allocation by comparing their input-output ratios to those of others. Perceived inequities—such as feeling under-rewarded relative to peers—may reduce motivation or provoke adaptive strategies. In the enterprise context, such perceptions may shape how male and female managers respond to structural barriers, influence strategic decisions, and affect enterprise outcomes. By linking objective disparities with subjective experiences of fairness, Equity Theory offers a valuable lens to interpret gender dynamics in resource access.

Financial inclusion refers to access to and use of affordable financial products and services by individuals and firms. It is commonly measured by indicators such as possession of bank accounts, access to credit, and availability of mobile financial services (Ozili, 2021; Barajas et al., 2020). Financial inclusion supports enterprise growth, reduces vulnerability to income shocks, and promotes equitable development (Arnold & Gammage, 2019). Despite global progress, gender disparities persist. Women, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, remain disproportionately excluded from formal financial systems. Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2013) report that only 65% of women globally had a financial account compared to 72% of men, with poor women being 28% less likely than poor men to hold a formal bank account. Yet, when financially included, women are shown to exercise greater agency over their earnings, directing them towards both productive investments and improved well-being (Field et al., 2016; Holloway et al., 2017). Financial access has been positively correlated with women's autonomy over employment decisions, marriage choices, time allocation, and productivity outcomes (Islam et al., 2014; Ashraf et al., 2010; Suri & Jack, 2016). These outcomes suggest that addressing gendered financial exclusion is central to inclusive entrepreneurial development.

Land remains one of the most crucial yet gender-contested resources in enterprise development. Across many African contexts, women's access to and control over land is severely limited by patriarchal norms, discriminatory laws, and inheritance practices that privilege male relatives (Chigbu, 2019; Oziegbe-Anozie, 2020). Such gendered exclusions are not only symbolic of broader inequalities but also materially restrict women's ability to use land as collateral for accessing credit or starting businesses (Efobi et al., 2019). Two dominant explanations for women's land marginalisation emerge in the literature. The first attributes inequality to the disruption of traditional tenure

systems through colonial and postcolonial interventions, which led to the fragmentation and bureaucratisation of land regimes (Makamani & Wabomba, 2019). From this perspective, decolonial reforms are required to restore gender-sensitive communal access. The second explanation focuses on entrenched gender ideologies that normalise male control over land. As Chigbu (2020) argues, ‘son power’, ‘husband power’, and ‘father power’ structure land access in ways that render women’s rights contingent upon their relationships with men. In practice, this results in widespread landlessness among women, as shown by data indicating that 41% of African women do not independently own land, compared to 15% of men (UN Women, 2015). Empirical evidence from across Africa reinforces this concern. Brixiová et al. (2020) found that lack of land ownership constrained female entrepreneurs’ ability to access credit and achieve profitability. Similarly, Orkaido and Youna (2020) observed that land access was the strongest predictor of business growth among women in Ethiopia. These findings point to the importance of land not only as a productive asset but as a strategic enabler of women’s entrepreneurial success.

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are foundational to contemporary business operations, influencing everything from communication to e-commerce and digital finance. ICTs encompass a range of tools and systems—including hardware, software, and telecommunications—that facilitate information access, processing, and distribution (Porter & Millar, 1985; Maquire et al., 2007). Integration of ICT into enterprise operations improves efficiency, market reach, and innovation capacity (Clarke et al., 2009). However, the gender digital divide remains a barrier, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. According to the ITU (2021), the global internet penetration rate was 57% for women compared to 62% for men. This gap is especially pronounced in Africa, where only 19% of women use the internet, compared to 31% of men (Broadband Commission, 2017). Socio-cultural norms, limited digital literacy, and affordability issues exacerbate this divide. Moreover, online platform participation remains male-dominated; a 2018 OECD survey found that 65% of SMEs on Facebook were managed by men. The consequence is that women entrepreneurs without access to ICTs are disadvantaged in terms of visibility, market integration, and competitiveness. Thus, addressing the digital gender divide is imperative not only for equity but also for enhancing the overall effectiveness and reach of women-led enterprises in the digital economy.

Corruption undermines business performance by introducing uncertainty, increasing costs, and discouraging investment (Ezebilo et al., 2019; Nam et al., 2020). It has been shown to reduce firm-level efficiency and negatively affect innovation and growth (Ivanović-Djukić et al., 2019). While difficult to measure directly, perceptions of corruption—such as bribery experiences—serve as useful proxies in enterprise surveys. The gendered impact of corruption remains contested. Some studies suggest that women entrepreneurs are more discouraged by corruption due to their limited experience in negotiating bribes and lower tolerance for unethical practices (Statnik et al., 2022). Others, like Wellalage et al. (2019), report that in some South Asian contexts, bribery was more effective for women than for men in overcoming credit constraints. Nevertheless, the prevailing literature suggests that corruption disproportionately affects women, not simply because they are more ethical or risk-averse (Swamy et al., 2001; Charness & Gneezy, 2012), but because patriarchal power relations limit their access to corrupt networks and reinforce their marginality (Bullock & Jenkins, 2020). Goel and Nelson (2019) observed that women entrepreneurs generally perceive corruption to be lower than men, possibly reflecting differences in exposure or participation in informal influence networks. Given these mixed findings, corruption is included in this study not only as a business constraint but as a gendered phenomenon that may influence resource access and enterprise outcomes differently for men and women.

To better understand the gendered dynamics in access to resources for enterprise management, this study draws on two interrelated theoretical lenses: Human Capital Theory and Equity Theory. Together, these frameworks offer insight into both the structural and perceptual dimensions of gender-based differences in enterprise outcomes. Human Capital Theory (HCT) posits that individuals and groups accumulate

knowledge, skills, experience, and competencies—collectively referred to as human capital—which enhance their productivity and economic potential (Becker, 1964). Within the enterprise context, access to resources such as finance, land, and ICT can be seen as both a reflection and a determinant of human capital development. From this perspective, differences in access to credit or technological tools may stem from disparities in training, education, and work experience, all of which influence how entrepreneurs are perceived and how they perform. HCT is particularly useful for interpreting gender disparities in financial inclusion and managerial roles. For instance, if women have historically faced limited opportunities for formal employment or education, this may explain lower representation in ownership or management, and reduced access to financial instruments. However, the theory also provides a policy anchor: targeted investment in women's training, digital skills, and leadership development can yield substantial returns in enterprise growth and economic equity. Complementing HCT, Equity Theory (ET) offers a psychosocial perspective. First developed by Adams (1963), ET asserts that individuals assess fairness by comparing their input–output ratios to those of others. In organisational and entrepreneurial settings, perceived inequities—whether in land access, recognition, or administrative burdens—can lead to dissatisfaction, demotivation, or disengagement. In the context of this study, Equity Theory helps to interpret findings where male entrepreneurs perceive themselves to face more barriers in areas like land cost and telecommunications. These perceptions may signal a shift in gendered expectations and a redefinition of what equitable resource distribution looks like in practice. Together, Human Capital Theory and Equity Theory offer a multi-dimensional framework for examining how gender shapes access, performance, and perceptions in enterprise management. While HCT foregrounds the developmental pathways of skills and opportunities, ET highlights the relational and emotional responses to resource inequalities. This integrated approach enables a more holistic understanding of both structural and behavioural patterns within Namibia's enterprise sector.

3.0 The status of enterprises in Namibia

Namibia's enterprise sector plays a crucial role in national development, particularly in a context where traditional industries such as mining, agriculture, and fisheries have limited expansion capacity. Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are recognised as key drivers of employment creation, income generation, and inclusive economic growth. This section provides an overview of enterprise characteristics in Namibia, drawing primarily on the most recent Census of Business Establishments (2019–2021), and links them to broader debates on resource access and gender equity. According to the National Statistics Agency, Namibia had a total of 96,960 mapped business establishments, of which 61,502 were successfully enumerated. Of these, 90.7% were classified as micro-enterprises, followed by 6.4% small, 2.3% medium, and only 0.6% large enterprises. This overwhelmingly micro-character of the business landscape signals a fragile industrial base, where most enterprises operate on narrow margins and limited capital (NSA, 2022). More than half (51.2%) of these enterprises were established in the five years preceding the census, indicating a youthful and dynamic entrepreneurial landscape. Yet, high business discontinuation rates—reported at 12%—suggest structural challenges in ensuring enterprise survival. The average number of jobs created by established businesses remains low (3.2 jobs), raising concerns about the sustainability and transformative potential of these enterprises in addressing unemployment and inequality. Gender-disaggregated data reveal that women's participation in business is substantial, though unevenly distributed across ownership and management. While female participation in business ownership was estimated at 41% in 2015, actual female ownership stood at 26% (Venditto et al., 2020). This discrepancy suggests that women may frequently serve as co-owners or minority shareholders without significant decision-making power. In managerial terms, 36% of enterprises are led by women, which represents a relatively strong presence but still points to a gender gap in leadership within the enterprise sector. A significant portion of enterprises in Namibia operate informally—unregistered and unregulated by formal institutions. Common reasons for informality include unaffordable registration costs, lack of premises, and limited knowledge of the benefits of formalisation (Schöneburg-Schultz & Schultz,

2006; Rätty, 2010). Informality limits access to credit, land rights, and legal protections, and disproportionately affects women, who are more likely to be excluded from formal channels of capital and land acquisition. In terms of legal status, the majority of enterprises in Namibia are sole proprietorships (62.9%), followed by close corporations (20.2%) and government-owned or NGO-run entities. These forms of ownership suggest that enterprise development is largely driven by individuals rather than corporate or cooperative formations. Recognising the role of enterprise development in structural transformation, the Namibian government has prioritised SME growth through its Strategic Plan (2017–2022). Vision 2030 positions small businesses as central to employment creation and economic empowerment. However, despite contributing an estimated 20% of employment and 12% of GDP, Namibian SMEs face numerous constraints: lack of start-up and working capital, high interest rates, insufficient collateral, and limited financial literacy (Mukata & Swanepoel, 2017).

The structural realities of Namibia’s enterprise ecosystem—its high informality, weak capital base, and low job-creation rates—intersect meaningfully with gender dynamics. Women-managed enterprises are more likely to be informal, undercapitalised, and excluded from credit and land ownership systems. The predominance of sole proprietorships and informal businesses amplifies the role of personal networks and informal norms, which often reinforce patriarchal exclusionary practices. Moreover, the limited capacity of SMEs to formalise or scale up may be linked not only to market constraints but also to the continued gender-based inequalities in access to key operational resources. These dynamics necessitate a gender-sensitive approach to enterprise policy, one that does not merely focus on statistical representation but also interrogates structural power relations and access asymmetries. In this light, the subsequent sections of the paper examine, using empirical evidence, how these enterprise patterns translate into differences in access to finance, land, and ICTs, and how perceptions of corruption are experienced across gender lines.

4.0 Methodological underpinnings

This study investigates whether gender influences access to key managerial resources—specifically finance, land, and information and communication technologies (ICT)—within the operational management of enterprises in Namibia. The central research question is: Does gender continue to shape access to these resources in Namibia’s enterprise sector, despite efforts toward formal empowerment? A secondary objective is to assess whether perceived corruption introduces gendered barriers in enterprise operations. To answer these questions, the study draws on the Namibia Enterprise Survey Dataset (NESD), compiled by the World Bank between April 2014 and February 2015. The survey targeted private sector establishments in the manufacturing and services sectors. It aimed to provide firm-level data on the investment climate and business environment, including access to resources, infrastructure, and governance indicators. A total of 580 enterprises were interviewed using a stratified random sampling approach, covering the regions of Windhoek/Okahandja (42%), Walvis Bay/Swakopmund (31%), and Oshakati/Ongwediva (27%). Although a newer Namibia Enterprise Survey (2024/25) has recently been released, this study is based on the 2014/15 dataset, which was the most current available at the time of data extraction and analysis. Future research could build on these findings by comparing trends across the two survey periods to assess progress in gendered enterprise access.

The primary unit of analysis is the establishment, defined as a single physical location where business operations occur, with distinct financial statements and management structures. Enterprises included in the sample vary by size, ownership, sector, and managerial profile. The data provide information on gender of ownership and management, access to financial services and land, ICT use, and exposure to or perception of corruption. Of particular interest to this study is the gender of the top manager, used as a proxy variable to categorise enterprises as either female-managed or male-managed. This variable allows for comparative analysis of how different enterprise resources are accessed

and experienced based on managerial gender.

Four key domains were identified for analysis, and corresponding indicators were selected based on theoretical relevance and data availability within the NESD. These include:

1. Financial inclusion: access to checking/savings accounts, overdraft facilities, mobile money services, and lines of credit.
2. Land access: land ownership, leasing arrangements, use of land as collateral, and perception of land-related obstacles.
3. ICT use: communication via email, having a business website, and perceived barriers in telecommunications.
4. Corruption: perceived obstacles due to corruption and incidences of bribe requests in acquiring licenses, permits, and basic services.

The indicator variables were drawn directly from NESD question codes (e.g., k6 for checking accounts, g1a for land ownership, c22da for email use, j30f for corruption perceptions), and categorised into dichotomous variables (e.g., Yes/No responses). These indicators serve as proxies for actual access, perceived barriers, and institutional experiences relevant to enterprise management.

The analysis proceeded in three stages. The first stage is about descriptive statistics. Basic frequencies and cross-tabulations were generated to describe gender-based differences in access to finance, land, ICTs, and experiences of corruption. The second stage is about comparative analysis. Enterprises were disaggregated based on the gender of the top manager to assess differences in the selected indicators. This provided insight into gendered patterns across resource categories. The third stage is about statistical testing. The independent samples t-test was employed to test whether the mean differences in the selected indicators between male-managed and female-managed enterprises were statistically significant. The null hypothesis in each case was that there is no gender-based difference in the given indicator. A p-value threshold of 0.05 was used to determine significance.

Although some of the indicator variables were categorical, the t-test was applied for consistency across indicators and due to the large sample size, which allows for approximate normality assumptions. However, where proportions were used and justified, the t-test served as a robustness check of whether reported differences were statistically meaningful. While more complex modelling techniques (e.g., logistic regression) could have offered additional nuance, the choice of t-tests was guided by the paper's exploratory design and emphasis on comparison rather than prediction. This approach is appropriate for assessing whether observable differences exist between groups based on gender and can signal areas for further, more targeted quantitative or mixed-method research.

5.0 Findings

This section presents the key empirical findings based on the Namibia Enterprise Survey Dataset. It first outlines the characteristics of the sampled enterprises and their managers. It then analyses gender-based differences in access to finance, land, ICTs, and experiences of corruption. The results of the independent samples t-test are presented and interpreted to assess whether observed differences between male- and female-managed enterprises are statistically significant.

5.1 Characteristics of the surveyed enterprises

The ages of the establishments range from less than one year to 121 years by the end of the 2015 survey. Table 1 presents the period of establishment for the enterprises.

Table 1: Period of establishment of enterprises

Period	Frequency	Percentage
1894–1989	30	6.6%
1990–1999	85	18.7%
2000–2009	234	51.5%
2010–2014	105	23.1%
Total	454	100%

More than half of the enterprises (51.5%) were established between 2000 and 2009. Notably, 84% of the enterprises were formally registered by 2015, suggesting a largely formalised sample. Managerial experience was generally high: 76% of top managers had over ten years of experience, while only 8% had less than five years. In terms of ownership, 45% of enterprises had at least one woman among their owners. However, only 36% of the enterprises were managed by a female top manager. Table 2 summarises the legal structure of the surveyed firms.

Table 2: Shareholding and legal status

Legal Status	Frequency	Percentage
Shareholding company with traded shares	7	1%
Shareholding company with non-traded shares	14	3%
Sole proprietorship	201	43%
Partnership	27	6%
Limited partnership	220	47%
Total	469	100%

The firms spanned various sectors, with the highest representation in retail (33%), followed by construction (16%), and vehicle services (7%). Table 3 displays this sectoral distribution.

Table 3: Sectoral distribution of enterprises

Sector	Frequency	Percentage
Retail	184	33.0%
Construction	90	16.2%
Motor vehicle services	41	7.4%
Furniture	34	6.1%
Hotel and restaurants	29	5.2%
Food	28	5.0%
Others (various sectors)	151	27.1%
Total	557	100.0%

5.2 Gender-based differences in access to resources and corruption experiences

Using gender of the top manager as the basis for comparison, cross-tabulations were conducted across four resource domains: finance, land, ICT, and corruption. Table 4 summarises the percentage of male- and female-managed enterprises reporting access or constraints in each area.

Table 4: Summary of access indicators by gender (selected results)

Indicator	Women (%)	Men (%)	p-value	Significant
Own land 50% or more	15	37	0.0016	Yes
Access to land is an obstacle	30	46	0.0029	Yes
Cost of land is an obstacle	32	52	0.0003	Yes
Telecommunications is an obstacle	16	21	0.0105	Yes
Line of credit or loan	8	23	0.1974	No
Checking/savings account	35	62	0.7000	No
Corruption is an obstacle	20	29	0.0914	No

The results show significant gender differences in land-related variables. Male-managed enterprises are more likely to own land (37% vs. 15%) but also perceive access and cost of land as greater obstacles. This paradox suggests that land ownership among men may be more formal but also burdened with higher expectations or bureaucratic hurdles. A statistically significant difference was also observed in the perception of telecommunications as an obstacle (21% among men, 16% among women), indicating possible differences in digital

engagement or infrastructure dependency. By contrast, no statistically significant gender differences were found in access to banking services, use of mobile money, or corruption indicators. This could signal progress in formal equality or indicate that corruption and financial inclusion barriers are experienced broadly across gender lines in Namibia.

5.3 Summary of key findings

The findings from the Namibia Enterprise Survey reveal both convergence and divergence in how male- and female-managed enterprises experience access to key resources. Approximately 45 percent of the surveyed enterprises reported having women among their owners, while 36 percent were under the management of a female top executive. These figures indicate a relatively strong presence of women in enterprise ownership and leadership, although men still hold the majority of top managerial roles. Access to land emerged as a particularly significant area of gender-based difference. Male-managed enterprises were substantially more likely to own more than 50 percent of the land on which they operated. Paradoxically, however, men were also more likely than women to perceive access to land and the cost of land as major obstacles to their business operations. This suggests that although men may have greater formal land holdings, they may also encounter more structural or regulatory burdens associated with land ownership. In terms of ICT usage, the results indicated a relatively balanced pattern of access across gender lines. However, a larger proportion of male-managed enterprises reported telecommunications as a barrier to effective operations, implying potential differences in technological dependence, sectoral needs, or infrastructure quality. While not conclusive, this finding invites further investigation into how digital infrastructure intersects with gendered patterns of enterprise activity. With respect to financial access and experiences of corruption, the study found no statistically significant differences between female- and male-managed enterprises. Both groups reported relatively similar levels of access to credit, banking services, and experiences with bribery or corrupt practices. This may point to progress in closing gender gaps in financial services, or it may indicate that both groups face similar structural barriers in these domains. Overall, these results suggest that gender is not a uniform predictor of resource exclusion or access. While some areas, such as finance and corruption, appear to be largely gender-neutral, persistent gaps remain in land access and technological obstacles. These domains reflect deeper structural patterns shaped by historical inequalities, institutional design, and gendered expectations. The discussion that follows explores these findings in greater depth, situating them within the broader scholarly and policy discourse on gender equity and enterprise development in Namibia.

6. Discussion of key findings and conclusion

The findings of this study offer new empirical insights into the gender dynamics of enterprise management in Namibia, especially concerning access to land, finance, ICTs, and experiences with corruption. While some indicators reveal minimal differences between male- and female-managed enterprises, others highlight persistent structural disparities, particularly in land access and telecommunications. This section interprets these results through the lens of existing literature and considers their broader implications for gender equity and enterprise policy.

The finding that 45 percent of enterprises had women among their owners and that 36 percent were managed by female top executives suggests measurable progress in gender inclusion. In comparative terms, this level of participation is relatively high for a Sub-Saharan African country and reflects both policy-driven and social efforts toward women's economic empowerment. However, as Cornwall and Rivas (2015) remind us, representation alone does not equate to transformation. Effective gender equality requires that participation be

accompanied by decision-making power, resource control, and freedom from structural constraints. The ownership data in this study, for instance, do not tell us whether female owners hold majority shares or influence, indicating the need to distinguish between nominal and substantive ownership.

A particularly striking finding is the difference in land ownership: 37 percent of male-managed enterprises reported owning 50 percent or more of their operational land, compared to just 15 percent among female-managed firms. This confirms what earlier studies have established—that land remains a deeply gendered resource in Africa. As Chigbu (2019) and Oziegbe-Anozie (2020) argue, women’s land rights are often constrained by customary norms, patriarchal inheritance systems, and institutional inertia, which collectively limit women’s ability to secure and leverage land for business purposes. Moreover, the finding that male managers perceive land access and cost as significant obstacles complicates the narrative. It suggests that while men may hold land titles, they too encounter barriers such as high transaction costs, regulatory delays, or speculative pricing—obstacles that may be less visible to women simply because they are excluded from ownership in the first place. This complexity underscores the need to move beyond binary comparisons and explore how gendered structures interact with broader political and economic systems.

ICT usage, by contrast, showed near parity between male- and female-managed firms in basic access, such as the use of email or business websites. However, male-managed enterprises reported greater difficulty with telecommunications infrastructure. This could reflect sectoral differences: men may be more likely to manage enterprises in industries requiring high-speed connectivity or complex supply chains. Alternatively, it may reflect a different sensitivity to technological barriers, shaped by expectations of scale or growth. While the digital gender divide remains a global concern (ITU, 2021), Namibia’s narrowing gap in ICT usage among managers could signal the success of digital inclusion policies and growing digital literacy among women entrepreneurs.

Notably, no significant gender differences were found in access to financial services or in experiences of corruption. This finding deserves cautious interpretation. On the one hand, it suggests that financial inclusion strategies may be working, gradually levelling the playing field. Studies such as those by Holloway et al. (2017) and Suri and Jack (2016) have shown that mobile banking and microfinance initiatives can empower women and increase their financial agency. On the other hand, the absence of a gender gap in corruption experiences may indicate that all entrepreneurs—regardless of gender—face similar bureaucratic and institutional challenges. As Goel and Nelson (2019) note, corruption is often embedded in relational networks of power that cut across gender lines, even if they are historically male-dominated. In contexts where formal safeguards are weak, both male- and female-owned firms may be equally vulnerable to coercive or extractive demands.

Taken together, these findings support three key arguments. First, there is evidence that women’s empowerment in enterprise management is occurring, particularly in terms of representation and access to ICTs. This reflects both policy commitments and broader social shifts. Second, the data confirm that Namibia’s history of gender-sensitive legal reforms and strategic planning—such as the constitutional commitment to equality and the emphasis on SME development in Vision 2030—has yielded tangible outcomes. However, these gains are uneven, particularly in domains where deeply entrenched norms, like land ownership, remain resistant to change. Third, the findings point to the emergence of a new gendered equilibrium in which traditional expectations are being reconfigured. The fact that men increasingly report obstacles in domains once dominated by male privilege—such as land access or telecommunications—may indicate a recalibration of masculine norms, as power becomes more diffuse and contested.

This shifting terrain calls for a renewed focus on structural transformation, not only in policy but in practice. Addressing gender equity in enterprise development cannot rely solely on increasing participation; it must confront the institutional and cultural systems that reproduce exclusion, even as legal frameworks improve. Land reform, digital infrastructure, and anti-corruption enforcement must all be approached with gender sensitivity, informed by both data and lived experience. The next section turns to specific recommendations for policy and practice, drawing on the empirical evidence to suggest pathways toward a more equitable and sustainable enterprise environment in Namibia.

These dynamics resonate with principles of Equity Theory in HRM, where perceptions of distributive injustice—whether regarding land, technology, or formal recognition—can erode motivation, weaken organisational commitment, and prompt adaptive (or even withdrawal) behaviour. The findings that male managers increasingly perceive barriers in historically male-dominated domains may reflect a shift in comparative reference groups and expectations. For women, persistent structural exclusion from land and leadership suggests that both material and psychological equity remain unfulfilled. These insights reinforce the importance of integrating HRM approaches in enterprise development, not only to enhance resource access but to build perceptions of fairness and belonging within business ecosystems.

7. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

This study set out to investigate whether gender continues to influence access to key enterprise resources—namely finance, land, ICTs, and corruption experiences—within the Namibian business environment. Drawing on data from the 2014/2015 Namibia Enterprise Survey, the analysis revealed a complex pattern of both gender convergence and divergence. While no statistically significant gender differences were found in access to finance or experiences of corruption, important disparities emerged in land ownership and perceived barriers related to telecommunications. Women remain significantly underrepresented in land ownership and face indirect exclusion from critical productive assets. At the same time, male-managed firms appear to encounter higher perceived barriers in land-related transactions and technological infrastructure, suggesting an evolving resource environment. These findings highlight both progress and unfinished work in the pursuit of gender equity in Namibia's enterprise sector. On one hand, women's participation in business management has visibly expanded, supported by constitutional reforms and national development strategies that promote inclusivity. On the other, substantive gendered inequalities endure in areas where patriarchal norms remain institutionally entrenched. The evidence suggests that gender equity does not automatically follow legal equality; it must be cultivated through targeted, sustained, and context-responsive policies. This study reaffirms that gender matters in enterprise management—not always in the ways anticipated, and not uniformly across all resource domains, but consistently enough to warrant deeper policy attention. Namibia's legal and institutional frameworks provide a strong foundation for gender inclusion, yet realising their transformative potential requires continued engagement with the lived experiences of both women and men in the entrepreneurial sphere. A new normal is not inevitable; it must be imagined, constructed, and sustained.

7.2 Policy recommendations

In this light, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

1. Prioritise gender-sensitive land reform policies. Given the persistent gender gap in land ownership, land reform programmes must go beyond legal recognition and address the social and cultural dynamics that limit women's land rights. This includes sensitising traditional authorities, reforming inheritance laws, and ensuring that land titling programmes are accessible to and inclusive of women entrepreneurs.
2. Integrate gender analysis into SME development programmes. Support structures for small and medium enterprises should be tailored to reflect gender-specific constraints. Enterprise development services—such as access to credit, legal registration, and capacity-building—must incorporate gender audits and ensure outreach to women in both urban and rural contexts.
3. Expand digital infrastructure with equity lenses. While ICT usage appears balanced overall, male-managed enterprises report greater challenges with telecommunications. Investments in digital infrastructure should consider the differing needs and contexts of both women- and men-managed enterprises, especially in remote or under-served regions. Training programmes in digital literacy for women entrepreneurs can further bridge the digital gender divide.
4. Strengthen anti-corruption mechanisms that account for gendered vulnerabilities. Although no major gender differences in corruption experiences were detected in this study, other literature suggests that corruption may affect women differently, especially in informal contexts. Public integrity systems should engage women business leaders in anti-corruption strategies and support platforms where female entrepreneurs can report corruption without fear of retaliation.
5. Build longitudinal data systems for gender and enterprise analysis. To track progress over time, Namibia's national surveys and enterprise datasets should include gender-disaggregated data not only on ownership and management but also on financial performance, value chains, and access to public procurement. This would help inform more precise and adaptive policies.
6. Promote inclusive masculinities in enterprise leadership. The finding that male managers increasingly perceive certain obstacles—particularly in land and ICT—suggests shifting gender norms and roles. Rather than viewing this as a loss of privilege, it presents an opportunity to reframe masculinity in terms of shared leadership, collaboration, and collective resilience. Policy discourse should embrace this shift and foster male allyship in advancing gender equity.

7.3 Areas for Further Research

This study provides a snapshot of gendered access to enterprise resources within Namibia, using nationally representative survey data and focusing on measurable indicators. While it reveals important patterns and shifts, it also raises several questions that warrant deeper and more nuanced investigation. It has contributed to the understanding of gender and enterprise resource access in Namibia, but it also opens space for deeper and more contextualised explorations. Bridging quantitative breadth with qualitative depth, and formal enterprise data with informal realities, will be crucial for building an inclusive, evidence-based agenda for gender-responsive enterprise development. To advance knowledge and inform policy more effectively, the following areas for further research are proposed:

1. Longitudinal analysis of gendered enterprise performance. The present study is cross-sectional, limiting the ability to assess how gender dynamics evolve over time. Future research should adopt longitudinal designs to examine whether gender gaps in land

- ownership, ICT access, and managerial roles widen or narrow over time, particularly in response to new policy interventions or economic shocks.
2. Qualitative studies on women's lived experiences in enterprise management. Statistical indicators provide valuable insight, but they do not fully capture the everyday realities, negotiations, and strategies of women entrepreneurs. In-depth qualitative studies—using life histories, focus groups, or ethnographic methods—could illuminate how women navigate structural constraints, assert agency, and experience empowerment or exclusion in specific business contexts.
 3. The informal sector and invisible enterprise labour. This study focused on formally registered enterprises. Yet, many women operate in the informal economy where access to credit, land, and infrastructure is even more precarious. Research on informal businesses, household enterprises, and unpaid contributions by women in family firms would reveal important dimensions of gender and enterprise often overlooked in formal datasets.
 4. Gender and access to procurement and value chains. Access to procurement contracts, supplier networks, and value chains can be critical to enterprise growth. Future research should explore whether gender affects participation in public and private procurement opportunities, and what structural or institutional barriers may limit women's engagement in high-value sectors.
 5. Sectoral dynamics and intersectionality. Not all enterprises are the same. Studies that disaggregate findings by economic sector (e.g., retail, construction, ICT, manufacturing) and intersect gender with other social categories—such as age, region, education, or ethnicity—could provide a more detailed understanding of which women and men are most disadvantaged or advantaged in enterprise development.
 6. Gender-responsive impact evaluations of enterprise policy. As Namibia continues to implement SME support programmes, land reform, and digital inclusion strategies, it is vital to assess their gendered impacts. Rigorous mixed-method evaluations—grounded in gender analysis—can help determine whether these interventions are closing or reinforcing resource access gaps.
 7. Masculinities and shifting gender roles in enterprise. The finding that men increasingly perceive land and telecommunications as barriers points to changing masculinities and expectations of male enterprise roles. Research that focuses explicitly on male entrepreneurs and the construction of masculinities in economic life could enrich our understanding of how gender norms are being renegotiated in real time.

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